

The Influence of Social Media Influencers on Consumers' Purchase Intentions for Electric Cars Mediated by Brand Image, Consumer Attitude, and Moderated by Green Attitude

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study is to aim to analyze the effect of Social Media Influencers on consumer purchase intentions on Electric cars with Brand Image variables as mediation and Green Attitude Variables as moderation. The research sample in this study were consumers who used and did not use electric cars with knowledge about electric cars in Indonesia in the 2020-2024 research year. This research method uses a quantitative approach with data collection techniques through questionnaires distributed to social media users, users and non-users of electric cars in Indonesia. The theoretical framework is built based on the latest literature review on digital marketing, consumer behavior and sustainability issues in the automotive industry. The results of the study can be expected to contribute new insights into the effectiveness of Social Media Influencers in the context of environmentally friendly products on the topic of Electric cars. The practical implications of this study can help marketers and policy makers in designing effective communication strategies to increase the adoption of Electric vehicles in Indonesia.

KEYWORDS: Brand Image, Consumer Attitude, Green Attitude dan Purchase Intention, Social Media Influencer.

INTRODUCTION

Social media has transformed into an integral part of life, influencing how people communicate, socialize, seek information, and express themselves (Heiets et al., 2024). Social media is a digital platform useful for interacting, sharing content, and connecting with others online, with characteristics of users including interactivity, social networks, mobility, content sharing, and news sharing (Sarman & Çiftci, 2024).

Dependence on social media has become excessive for the Indonesian society, as much leisure time is spent surfing social media. The number of social media users in Indonesia has reached 167 million active users who use apps such as WhatsApp, Instagram, TikTok, YouTube, and Facebook (Cheah et al., 2024). Electric cars are vehicles that use electric motors as propulsion instead of internal combustion engines powered by fossil fuels, and electric cars are driven using rechargeable batteries as their main power source. The advantage of electric cars is that they produce environmentally friendly emissions with an electric propulsion system that is more efficient in converting electricity into driving power, with lower operational costs and minimal fuel and maintenance requirements. Furthermore, electric cars offer comfort with responsive and quiet acceleration while driving (Urooj & Nasir, 2024).

Electric cars are considered an environmentally friendly vehicle alternative, expected to help reduce environmental pollution caused by carbon emissions from vehicles. Carbon emissions are a significant contributor to climate change in Indonesia, with impacts on the environment, health, and economic instability (Ahmad & Zhang, 2020). With the issuance of Presidential Regulation No. 98 of 2021, aimed at reducing carbon dioxide emissions in Indonesia, the government has implemented policies regarding the use of electric vehicles, as stated in Presidential Regulation No. 55 of 2019 concerning the Acceleration of Battery Electric Vehicle Programs for Road Transportation (Shakeel, 2022). Electric cars represent a renewable innovation that benefits the environment by using one or more electric motors powered by rechargeable batteries, allowing the electric motor to provide instant torque, produce zero carbon emissions, and operate quietly (Flowers et al., 2022).

The role of Social Media Influencers can influence individuals or consumers through social media by playing a role in shaping environmentally friendly attitudes among consumers. Influencers do this through the content they create, which can increase consumer awareness of environmental issues and their impacts, and promote eco-friendly and sustainable lifestyles that can inspire followers to adopt environmentally friendly behavior (Hartmann & Apaolaza-Ibañez, 2012). Influencers with many followers can significantly

shape consumer attitudes toward environmental awareness, thereby influencing consumer purchase intentions toward eco-friendly products (Dlamini & Mahowa, 2024).

Green Attitude refers to an individual's environmentally friendly attitude, which is based on values, behaviors, and beliefs that encourage people to care for and take responsibility for preserving the environment. Individuals with green attitudes tend to be conscious of environmental preservation and strive to minimize the use of environmentally harmful products (Shi et al., 2023). Green Attitude is not only applicable to individuals but also to organizations, communities, and countries. Developing green attitudes in sustainable development can reduce negative environmental impacts, creating a positive trend for governments to encourage society to adopt green attitudes in their activities (Sohaib et al., 2022). Individuals who are environmentally conscious tend to have a positive influence on their purchasing intentions for eco-friendly products. These consumers believe that buying eco-friendly products contributes to environmental conservation efforts. Other factors, such as government policies, family and friends, and social norms, can also influence purchasing intentions (Wang et al., 2021).

Consumer attitude explains how a consumer's concern about the products they purchase can change their buying behavior. Consumers may be influenced by social media influencers to change their mindset and create a purchase intention for a product (Diógenes et al., 2017). A brand image can express the uniqueness of a product through social media by having a reputation that builds consumer trust in the product's quality. Trust is essential in promotions, helping to create a strong brand image in the eyes of consumers (Wicaksono & Masharionon, 2018). Collaborating with influencers can help brands introduce their products to consumers who are not yet familiar with them. Influencers can showcase the brand's products in content that provides a strong visual introduction, helping consumers remember the brand (Foroudi, 2019).

The grand theory that serves as the main foundation of this research is Social Influence Theory, which identifies three ways in which social influence is accepted: compliance, identification, and internalization. This theory defines social influence as a change in behavior within a social environment caused by one person or a group of people (Kelman, 1958). Compliance, identification, and internalization represent responses to social influence and can be seen as the result of a dynamic process of interaction with the influencer in the context of information and motivation. Understanding the differences between compliance, identification, and internalization is necessary for influence to have an effect on its recipient (Rodrigues, 2018). The relationship between the stages of stimulus evaluation and the related psychological processes results in a response to the stimulus, illustrating how a group of people can be influenced by interacting with an individual to gain meaning about social influence (Yasar et al., 2015).

Social media influencers have the ability to influence consumers' perceptions and preferences through the content they share on social media platforms (Al-Mu'ani et al., 2023). With a large number of followers and high credibility in specific industries, influencers can build strong relationships with their audience. The content shared, such as product reviews, recommendations, and testimonials, can shape positive perceptions of the promoted product or brand (Hasan & Sohail, 2020).

Through interactions between influencers and their followers, consumers can feel a sense of closeness and trust in the influencer. This can trigger the intention or desire to purchase products recommended by the influencer. This is supported by previous studies, such as those by (Venciute et al., 2023) on influencers in Lithuania, showing an impact on purchase intentions for fashion brands. (Foroudi, 2019) found an increase in hotel visit intentions in the United States due to the influence of social media influencers. This was also observed in the film industry, where (Mathys et al., 2016) found a significant influence of social media influencers on consumer purchase intentions through their content, as followers felt emotionally connected and inspired to adopt the preferences and consumption behaviors suggested by the influencer.

Social media has now become an effective tool for promoting products, making it easier to reach target consumers. Consumers who are environmentally conscious are a target for promoting electric cars (Masuda et al., 2022). Environmentally conscious consumers tend to use products that benefit environmental preservation (Suki, 2016). Therefore, consumers' environmental concerns can influence their purchase intentions for electric cars, which can be observed in the promotions conducted by influencers on social media. These promotions can create consumer attitudes toward purchasing electric cars to support environmental conservation (Wu & Long, 2024).

Social media influencers are a useful and effective way to promote products to reach target consumers. The role of influencers can affect consumer attitudes toward purchasing products through experiences or content created by influencers on social media (Nafees et al., 2021). The influence of an influencer, through the content or experiences they create, can positively impact consumers, leading them to develop positive attitudes toward products, which in turn can influence their purchase intentions (Thøgersen et al., 2015).

Consumer attitudes, which can change based on the consumer's perceptions, can negatively impact product sales. Therefore, influencers play a key role in influencing consumers' purchase intentions. Social media influencers can evoke a positive consumer attitude toward a product, encouraging purchase intentions (Chen et al., 2023).

Purchase decisions are influenced by various factors, one of which is the impact of social media influencers (Dwivedi et al., 2021). The relationship between these factors does not simply happen by chance; as found by (Chandra & Indrawati, 2023) and (Abdullah et al., 2023), the influence of social media influencers becomes more significant when a brand has a good image (Kumar et al., 2021). The intention to buy, which ultimately leads to the decision to consume a product, is shaped by the content shared by social media influencers who promote products with unique, reputable images that provide greater trust to consumers (Wicaksono & Masharionon, 2018). An influencer can help improve brand image through the content they create, fostering positive perceptions of a product or brand with content that promotes the product's value through reviews and experiences shared by the influencer (Nyagadza et al., 2023).

Creating a positive attitude toward a product can increase consumer purchase intention. Consumers tend to be more attracted to purchasing products from brands with a positive image, and the influence of an influencer can lead to increased sales (Feng et al., 2023). Positive consumer attitudes toward a product are likely to result in higher purchase intentions, but when consumers have a favorable assessment of a product's attributes, benefits, and value, they are more likely to consider buying it. Consumers typically seek harmony between their thoughts and feelings when purchasing a product, which can drive them to buy from a particular brand (Abdullah et al., 2023). Consumer attitudes also affect the perception of risk in purchasing; a positive attitude can lower perceived risk and increase purchase intention. Consumers may align their purchases with their self-image, and if they believe a product can strengthen their identity, this can further drive purchase intention (Garg et al., 2023).

Consumer attitudes play a crucial role in shaping purchase intentions, with positive attitudes increasing the likelihood of purchasing, while negative attitudes can hinder it (Li et al., 2024). Marketers and consumer behavior researchers must understand the nuances of consumer attitudes to more accurately predict and influence purchase intentions. Effective marketing strategies often focus on forming or reinforcing positive consumer attitudes as a key step in driving purchase intentions (Wang et al., 2023).

Brand image is associated with high perceived quality, so consumers are more likely to have strong purchase intentions toward brands perceived to have good quality. Trust in a positive brand image, built through consumer trust and credibility, can reduce the perception of risk and increase the likelihood of buying from that brand (Rao et al., 2021). A unique brand image can help a product stand out in the competition by providing differentiation that influences purchase intentions. When brands create distinct products, it can foster consumer loyalty, building positive attitudes toward the brand. Loyal consumers will have consistent purchase intentions and trust in the brand. Loyal consumers also provide positive reviews and recommend the brand to others, further increasing purchase intentions (Chen et al., 2024).

Brand image has a significant influence on purchase intention through various psychological and social mechanisms. A strong and positive brand image can substantially increase the likelihood that consumers will consider and eventually intend to purchase a product or service. Therefore, building and maintaining a positive brand image is a key marketing strategy for increasing consumer purchase intentions. Marketers need to focus on creating strong, positive, and relevant brand associations for their target market to maximize the impact of brand image on purchase intention (Kim & Park, 2023).

METHODOLOGY

The research design in this study serves as a strategy that outlines the methods and procedures for collecting and analyzing data (Souza & Rocha, 2019). This study adopts a quantitative research approach using an online survey method, with questionnaires distributed via Google Forms. The research is cross-sectional, meaning data is collected at a single point in time. The survey was distributed

through social media or the WhatsApp application, systematically and structurally describing the influence or causality of each variable to answer the research questions (Chen, 2024).

In this research, the causal relationship being examined focuses on the exogenous variables, namely the influence of Social Media Influencers on Consumer Purchase Intention for Electric Vehicles, mediated by Brand Image and Consumer Attitude, and moderated by Green Attitude. The endogenous variable is Purchase Intention (Chen, 2024).

RESULT AND ANALYSIS

This study employed an online questionnaire method to collect data from respondents with or without prior experience in using electric vehicles. From the distribution process, a total of 125 respondent data points were successfully gathered and further processed for analysis in line with the research objectives.

The questionnaire data collected from 125 respondents were classified based on their region of residence, gender, and age. The majority of respondents were male, accounting for 76 people (60.3%), while female respondents totaled 50 people (39.7%). Most respondents were between the ages of 18-30, comprising 86 people (68.3%), followed by the 30-40 age group with 18 people (14.3%), the 40-50 age group with 14 people (11.1%), and the 50-60 age group with 8 people (6.3%).

The respondents' regions of residence were spread across several major cities in Indonesia. Jakarta had the highest number of respondents, with 34 people (27%), followed by Bandung and Medan, each with 20 people (12%), Surabaya with 16 people (8%), and Makassar with 13 people (10.3%). This geographic distribution indicates a fairly diverse range of experiences and understanding among respondents regarding electric vehicles.

The analysis results in the study include testing the instrument, model structure, mediation test, and moderation test. The instrument tests covered internal consistency reliability, discriminant validity, and convergent validity. The structural model tests involved examining the R Square (R^2), hypothesis testing, and path analysis of the regression model.

Table 1. Results of Research Instrument Testing

Construct	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Brand Image	0,706	0,836	0,629
Consumer Attitude	0,871	0,912	0,721
Green Attitude	0,865	0,907	0,710
Purchase Intention	0,818	0,892	0,733
Social Media Influencer	0,923	0,935	0,592

Source: Data Processed (2024)

In this study, the consistency reliability was measured using Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values. Based on Table 1, the Cronbach's Alpha values for all tested variables, including Social Media Marketing, Consumer Attitude, Green Attitude, Purchase Intention, Social Media Influencer, and SMI-GA-PI, were found to be above 0.7. Specifically, the Cronbach's Alpha values for these variables were 0.706, 0.871, 0.865, 0.818, and 0.923, respectively, indicating good internal consistency.

The Composite Reliability values for all variables also showed satisfactory results, with values exceeding 0.7 for each variable. The Composite Reliability values for these variables were sequentially 0.836, 0.912, 0.907, 0.907, 0.892, and 0.935. Based on these testing results, it can be concluded that all variables in this study have good reliability, meaning that the research instrument can be relied upon to measure the intended constructs.

The discriminant validity in this study was assessed by examining the cross-loading values of each variable. The results of the testing, as shown in Table 2, indicate that the cross-loading values for the constructs of the studied variables yielded satisfactory results. Specifically, the cross-loading values for the variables Brand Image, Consumer Attitude, Green Attitude, Purchase Intention,

and Social Media Influencer were all greater than 0.7. These findings confirm that the discriminant validity of the research instrument has been met, meaning that each variable can be distinctly identified and effectively measures the intended constructs.

Table 2. The Estimation Results

Construct	Brand Image	Consumer Attitude	Green Attitude	Purchase Intention	Social Media Influencer
Brand Image	0.793				
Consumer Attitude	0.512	0.849			
Green Attitude	0.510	0.695	0.843		
Purchase Intention	0.632	0.698	0.647	0.856	
Social Media Influencer	0.561	0.667	0.599	0.666	0.769

Source: Data Processed (2024)

Convergent validity is a method used to measure the extent to which a measure correlates positively with alternative measures of the same construct. In this study, convergent validity is assessed by examining the loading factor values and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for each variable. The results of the convergent validity test can be seen in Table 3, which demonstrates how well each indicator within the research variables consistently measures the intended construct.

The R-squared analysis shows the contribution of the independent variables to the dependent variable in the research model. The Purchase Intention variable has the highest R-squared value of 0.633, meaning that 63.3% of its variance can be explained by the Social Media Influencer variable. Meanwhile, the Consumer Attitude variable has an R-squared value of 0.444, indicating that 44.4% of its variance can be explained by the Social Media Influencer variable. The Brand Image variable has the lowest R-squared value of 0.315, showing that 31.5% of its variance can be explained by the Purchase Intention variable, while the remaining variance for all variables is explained by factors outside this research model.

Table 3. R Square

Construct	R Square
Brand Image	0.315
Consumer Attitude	0.444
Purchase Intention	0.633

Source: Data Processed (2024)

The hypothesis testing results indicate that Brand Image has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Intention, with a t-statistic value of 2.56, which is greater than 1.96; thus, Hypothesis 1 is accepted. Consumer Attitude also positively and significantly affects Purchase Intention, with a t-statistic value of 2.343, which is greater than 1.96, leading to the acceptance of Hypothesis 2. Green Attitude has an effect on Purchase Intention at a 5% significance level, with a t-statistic value of 1.704, which is greater than 1.96, resulting in the acceptance of Hypothesis 3. However, Green Attitude does not play a moderating role in the relationship between Social Media Influencer and Purchase Intention, with a t-statistic value of 0.216, which is less than 1.96.

Social Media Influencer significantly affects several variables in this study. The effect of Social Media Influencer on Brand Image is significant, with a t-statistic value of 8.577, which is greater than 1.96, leading to the acceptance of Hypothesis 5. Social Media Influencer also significantly affects Consumer Attitude, with a t-statistic value of 9.059, which is greater than 1.96, resulting in the acceptance of Hypothesis 6. Additionally, Social Media Influencer has a significant effect on Purchase Intention, with a t-statistic value of 4.513, which is greater than 1.96, thus accepting Hypothesis 7.

Based on the hypothesis testing results, it can be concluded that Brand Image, Consumer Attitude, and Green Attitude positively influence Purchase Intention. Social Media Influencer also positively affects Brand Image, Consumer Attitude, and Purchase Intention. However, the moderating role of Green Attitude in the relationship between Social Media Influencer and Purchase Intention is not proven in this study.

These findings indicate that marketing strategies focusing on enhancing Brand Image, Consumer Attitude, and utilizing Social Media Influencers can be effective in increasing Purchase Intention. While Green Attitude affects Purchase Intention, its role as a moderator is not significant in the context of the influence of Social Media Influencer. The results of this study provide valuable insights for marketers in designing effective communication and marketing strategies, particularly in leveraging the role of Social Media Influencer.

The results of the regression model testing, as seen in Table 4, are interpreted from the data analysis. The original sample estimate analysis indicates that Brand Image has a positive influence on Purchase Intention with a value of 0.272. Consumer Attitude also shows a positive influence on Purchase Intention with a value of 0.289. Green Attitude has a positive influence on Purchase Intention with a value of 0.183. The influence of Social Media Influencer, moderated by Green Attitude, on Purchase Intention shows a positive value of 0.014. These findings indicate that improvements in each of these variables tend to increase Purchase Intention.

Social Media Influencer has a significant positive influence on several variables in this study. The influence of Social Media Influencer on Brand Image shows a positive value of 0.561. Social Media Influencer also has a positive influence on Consumer Attitude with a value of 0.667. The direct influence of Social Media Influencer on Purchase Intention is also positive with a value of 0.546. These results demonstrate that Social Media Influencer plays an important role in influencing various aspects of consumer behavior. This finding emphasizes the importance of marketing strategies involving Social Media Influencer in efforts to enhance Brand Image, Consumer Attitude, and Purchase Intention.

Based on the analysis results, it can be concluded that all variables studied have a positive influence on Purchase Intention. Brand Image, Consumer Attitude, and Green Attitude each have a positive contribution to increasing Purchase Intention. Social Media Influencer has a strong positive influence, not only directly on Purchase Intention but also on Brand Image and Consumer Attitude. Although the moderating effect of Green Attitude on the relationship between Social Media Influencer and Purchase Intention is positive, its value is relatively small compared to the direct influence of the other variables.

These results have important implications for marketing and communication strategies. Companies can leverage the role of Social Media Influencer to enhance Brand Image and Consumer Attitude, which in turn can increase Purchase Intention. Strategies focused on improving Brand Image and Consumer Attitude can also be effective in enhancing Purchase Intention. Although Green Attitude has a positive influence, its role as a moderator does not seem to be significant in the context of the influence of Social Media Influencer on Purchase Intention.

This study provides valuable insights for marketers in designing effective communication and marketing strategies. Utilizing Social Media Influencer can be an effective strategy to enhance Brand Image, Consumer Attitude, and ultimately Purchase Intention. However, marketers also need to pay attention to the importance of building a strong Brand Image and shaping a positive Consumer Attitude independently. Although the Green Attitude aspect shows a positive influence, strategies overly focused on this aspect may not yield significant impacts compared to other factors in the context of the influence of Social Media Influencer on Purchase Intention.

The mediating role of Brand Image in the influence of Social Media Influencer on Purchase Intention was tested using the Sobel test calculator and Smart PLS processing results. The analysis results show the coefficient of influence $X \rightarrow M$ of 0.667, $M \rightarrow Y$ of 0.289, with standard errors of 0.074 and 0.123 respectively, resulting in a t-statistic value of 2.273, which is greater than the critical value of 1.96. Based on these results, it can be concluded that Brand Image has a significant role in mediating the influence of Social Media Influencer on Purchase Intention.

Table 4. Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Original Estimate	Sample Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Values
Brand Image -> Purchase Intention	0.272	0.106	2.556	0.005
Consumer Attitude -> Purchase Intention	0.289	0.123	2.343	0.010
Green Attitude -> Purchase Intention	0.183	0.107	1.704	0.044
Social Media Influencer X Green Attitude X Purchase Intention	0.014	0.065	0.216	0.415
Social Media Influencer -> Brand Image	0.561	0.065	8.577	0.000
Social Media Influencer -> Consumer Attitude	0.667	0.074	9.059	0.000
Social Media Influencer -> Purchase Intention	0.546	0.121	4.513	0.000

Source: Data Processed (2024)

The mediating role of Consumer Attitude in the influence of Social Media Influencer on Purchase Intention was tested using the Sobel test calculator and Smart PLS processing results. The analysis shows the coefficient of influence X->M of 0.561 and M->Y of 0.272, with a standard error for X->M of 0.065, resulting in a calculated t-value of 2.456, which exceeds the critical value of 1.96. Based on these results, it can be concluded that Consumer Attitude has a significant role in mediating the influence of Social Media Influencer on Purchase Intention.

Table 5. Mediation of Social Media Influencer, Brand Image, and Purchase Intention

Variable	Input	
	Coefficient	Standard Error
SMI-BI	0,667	0,074
BI-PI	0,289	0,123
Sobel Test	2,273	

Source: Data Processed (2024)

Table 6. Mediation of Social Media Influencer on Consumer Attitude and Purchase Intention

Variable	Input	
	Coefficient	Standard Error
SMI-CA	0,561	0,065
CA-PI	0,272	0,106
Sobel Test	2,456	

Source: Data Processed (2024)

The results of the moderation analysis indicate that Green Attitude does not play a significant role in moderating the relationship between Social Media Influencer and Purchase Intention, with a t-statistic value of 0.216 and a p-value of 0.415 < 0.5. These findings suggest that the influence of Social Media Influencer on Purchase Intention is not significantly affected by the consumers' Green Attitude. This may be due to the presence of other factors that are more dominant in influencing the effectiveness of marketing through influencers. Therefore, a separate evaluation of the aspects of environmentally friendly product marketing within influencer marketing strategies is needed.

Figure 1. Outer Model
 Source: Smart PLS Processed Data

CONCLUSIONS

This study reveals the significant role of Social Media Influencers in influencing consumers' Purchase Intention towards electric vehicles in Indonesia, with Brand Image and Consumer Attitude acting as mediators. Brand Image, Consumer Attitude, and Green Attitude have been shown to have a positive and significant impact on Purchase Intention, highlighting the importance of marketing strategies focused on these aspects. Interestingly, Green Attitude does not play a moderating role in the relationship between Social Media Influencer and Purchase Intention, indicating that the influence of influencers is not dependent on consumers' environmental awareness levels. These findings provide important implications for marketing strategies in the automotive industry, particularly for environmentally friendly vehicles, where companies can leverage Social Media Influencers to enhance Brand Image and shape positive consumer attitudes. However, it is essential to note that while Green Attitude has a direct impact on Purchase Intention, marketing strategies related to this aspect should be considered separately from influencer marketing strategies.

The empirical contribution of this research to the digital marketing literature strengthens influence marketing theory and emphasizes the importance of social media influencer strategies in the digital age. This study expands the understanding of the psychological mechanisms underlying the effectiveness of social media influencers by revealing the mediating roles of brand image and consumer attitude, providing new insights into the cognitive and affective processes consumers undergo in responding to marketing messages through influencers. The findings regarding the non-significant moderating effect of green attitude open up opportunities for further academic discussion about the complexity of the interaction between environmental factors, influencer messages, and consumer purchase decisions in the context of marketing environmentally friendly products. The methodological contribution of this research lies in demonstrating the application of PLS-SEM analysis in testing complex models involving mediation and moderation effects. Finally, this study highlights the importance of considering demographic factors in digital marketing research, which could encourage further investigation into how demographic differences influence the effectiveness of influencer marketing strategies and consumer purchase intentions in specific product contexts, such as electric vehicles.

Based on the research findings, electric vehicle companies are advised to focus their marketing strategies on utilizing credible social media influencers relevant to their target market, given the significant positive impact on brand image, consumer attitude, and purchase intention. Companies need to ensure that the content shared by influencers can enhance brand image and positive consumer attitudes towards electric vehicles, considering the significant mediating role of both aspects. Although green attitude was not proven to significantly moderate the relationship between social media influencers and purchase intention, companies should still consider sustainability aspects in their marketing strategies due to its positive direct influence on purchase intention. Messages related to sustainability and the environmental benefits of electric vehicles can be integrated into influencer campaigns, but should not be the main focus. Finally, further research is needed to explore other factors that could moderate the effectiveness of social media influencers in the context of electric vehicle marketing, as well as to investigate how these strategies can be tailored to different consumer demographic characteristics.

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